

Through Penelope's Eyes: from Atwood to Homer
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1. Homer, *Odyssey*, 2. 94-122.

It's not the suitors here who deserve the blame,
it's... the matchless queen of cunning.
Look here. For three years now, getting on to four,
she's played it fast and loose with all our hearts,
building each man's hopes—
dangling promises, dropping hints to each—
but all the while with something else in mind.
This was her latest masterpiece of guile:
she set up a great loom in the royal halls
and she began to weave, and the weaving finespun,
the yarns endless, and she would lead us on: 'Young men,
my suitors, now that King Odysseus is no more,
go slowly, keen as you are to marry me, until
I can finish off this web...
so my weaving won't all fray and come to nothing.
This is a shroud for old lord Laertes, for that day
when the deadly fate that lays us out at last will take him down.
I dread the shame my countrywomen would heap upon me,
yes, if a man of such wealth should lie in state
without a shroud for cover.'

Her very words,
and despite our pride and passion we believed her.
So by day she'd weave at her great and growing web—
by night, by the light of torches set beside her,
she would unravel all she'd done. Three whole years
she deceived us blind, seduced us with this scheme...
Then, when the wheeling seasons brought the fourth year on,
one of her women, in on the queen's secret, told the truth
and we caught her in the act—unweaving her gorgeous web.
So she finished it off. Against her will. We forced her."

Trans. Robert Fagles

2. Ovid, *Heroides*, 1. 94-98

"Or are you a captive of love?
The hearts of men are fickle. Their eyes wander.
Do you sit with some femme fatale, joking about your
rustic
wife back home who is only good for weaving?"

Trans. David R. Slavitt

3. Ovid, *Heroides*, 1. 109, 113.

“a wild and rowdy throng
...assail me and beset my innocent life.”

Turba ruunt in me luxuriosa proci

Trans. David R. Slavitt

4. Ovid, *Heroides*, 1. 138-141

“Your son needs you now to teach him
how to be a man. Your father needs you also
and it is his prayer that you may return in time
to close his eyes on his last—and not so distant—day.”

Trans. David R. Slavitt

5. Atwood, *The Penelopiad*, p. 2

“Hadn’t I been faithful? Hadn’t I waited, and waited, and waited, despite the temptation—almost the compulsion—to do otherwise? And what did I amount to, once the official version gained ground? An edifying legend. A stick used to beat other women with.”

6. Atwood, *The Penelopiad*, p. 139

“The songs claim that the arrival of Odysseus and my decision to set the test of the bow and axes coincided by accident... [But] I knew that only Odysseus would be able to perform this archery trick. I knew that the beggar was Odysseus. There was no coincidence. I set the whole thing up on purpose.”

7. Atwood, *The Penelopiad*, p. 43

“Water does not resist. Water flows... Water is patient. Dripping water wears away a stone... Remember you are half water. If you can’t go through an obstacle, go around it. Water does.”